

THE INFLUENCE OF MICROSTRUCTURAL DAMAGE ON THE INTERNAL STRESS RESPONSE OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER APPLIED LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Tensile tests were carried out upon two aluminium/zirconia metal matrix composites in a neutron diffractometer. By combining mechanical testing of the composite with neutron diffraction, the build-up of lattice strain in both phases has been measured. The accumulation of microstructural damage throughout loading, was studied by standard optical and SEM techniques, together with the monitoring of the modulus of the composite. This allowed correlation of both the overall composite response to the applied stress, as well as the microstructural damage, with the mean lattice strain (stress) in both phases of the composite. Two composites were studied, one in which particle debonding was the dominant mechanism, and a second where particle cracking was widespread. The cracking was found to be dependent upon both particle volume and aspect ratio.

1. INTRODUCTION

Much research has been done in recent years on metal matrix composites (MMCs), due to their high stiffness and strength with respect to the unreinforced alloys. Despite the concerted effort in this area, practical applications of MMCs are limited by their low ductility and fracture toughness^{1,2}. The fracture mechanisms which dominate in MMCs include interfacial debonding leading to cavitation³, matrix voiding and particle fracture¹. All of these mechanisms are aided by the large internal stresses present due to the incorporation of a high stiffness reinforcement phase within a relatively low stiffness and low strength matrix. Here our aim has been to compare and contrast the stress transfer characteristics for materials in which particle cracking and interface debonding are the important damage mechanisms, through an examination of two different Al/ZrO₂ composites.

In a previous study⁴ we have quantified the effect of debonding upon the stress transfer in an Al/ZrO₂ composite made by a Vacuum Plasma Spray (VPS). This was done by measuring the decrease in the composite modulus during uniaxial straining and comparing the variation with modulus values calculated by the Eshelby model⁵⁻⁷ at various levels of debonding. The debonding levels predicted in this way have been shown to be in good agreement with the levels observed in the sections of the gauge length examined in a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) following the tensile test. As one would expect, debonding was found to be increasingly prevalent in the plastic region, leading to the development of a much smaller mean lattice stress in the reinforcement of the VPS material, as measured by neutron diffraction, than would have occurred if the particles had remained perfectly bonded. It was shown that the best agreement between the experimental data and the model is obtained when the debonded particles are taken to act as voids⁴.

Two aluminium/zirconia composite systems were compared in this work. The two materials were chosen because they were known to display different damage mechanisms - namely debonding and particle cracking. The mechanisms of microstructural damage which accumulate on loading, and

lead ultimately to failure of the composite, were quantitatively investigated by standard microscopic techniques, together with the monitoring of the composite modulus. By combining these observations with in-situ tensile tests performed in a neutron diffractometer, a relatively complete picture of the mechanical response of the composite can be gained. Neutron diffraction allows measurement of the mean lattice strains (stresses) in the bulk of the composite⁸ due to the relatively large penetration depth of neutrons in aluminium. The mean strain values obtained from the neutron diffraction data can be assessed using Eshelby models for the response of particulate MMCs⁵⁻⁷.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Composite Fabrication

Two composites were used in the present study. One was made in our Department by a VPS⁹ process using 6061 aluminium alloy matrix and 6.8 vol % of 25 μm diameter particulate zirconia reinforcement containing 4 wt % yttria. (The yttria acts as a stabiliser for the high temperature phases in the zirconia¹⁰.) This material was then forged, with a reduction of 40 %, to reduce the porosity inherent in VPS processed material. The second composite was produced by a Co-Spray ('CS') deposition process¹¹, using 2618 aluminium alloy matrix and 6 vol % of 12 μm particulate unstabilised zirconia reinforcement. The CS composite was subsequently extruded to a 25 mm cross-section. Houndsfield style tensile specimens were machined from both composites, solution treated and artificially aged to the peak aged condition.

Figure 1. The experimental neutron diffraction arrangement.

measuring, and then averaging, the shifts in positions of the most clearly defined diffraction peaks, the longitudinal lattice strain in the matrix and reinforcement were determined. The overall macroscopic composite strain was measured using strain gauges mounted on either side of the gauge length of the specimen. The stress / strain curve thus measured could then be compared directly with the elastic lattice strain development during the tests. A period of 4-6 hours was found to be necessary at each stress level for acceptable statistical accuracy in the location of the diffraction peaks. Once into the plastic region, an increasing degree of creep was observed as the stress levels were increased. At high loads creep strains of up to 0.3% were recorded while the specimen was held at constant load, which will limit the reliability of the data. However, the alternative option of maintaining the specimen at a constant length resulted in relaxation of the load by 5%, and this would have necessarily caused greater changes in the values of the elastic stress than might be expected for the former case.

2.2. Neutron Diffraction

Tensile tests were conducted in a slow strain rate testing rig designed to fit into a neutron diffractometer. The neutron diffraction measurements were performed at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, using the Polaris diffractometer¹². The experimental arrangement is shown in figure 1 and, in conjunction with the 'white' wavelength spectrum of the neutron beam at Rutherford Appleton, it allows simultaneous measurement of diffraction peaks from all sets of planes in both the axial and transverse directions.

Unfortunately, recent changes to the Polaris spectrometer meant that when the measurements were made on the CS composite the detector positions had been moved out of the horizontal plane by $\pm 22^\circ$. This necessitated tilting the testing rig to the correct orientation for the measurement of the axial diffraction peaks, and made simultaneous measurement of the transverse diffraction peaks impossible, since the testing rig was obscuring part of the outgoing beam. By

2.3. Mechanical Testing

A series of mechanical tests was performed upon both composites using a screw-driven Schenk mechanical testing machine at a strain rate of 0.1 mm/minute. These tests were performed on specimens prepared in the same manner as those used for the neutron diffraction tests. The aim was to obtain information about the relationship between damage evolution and the overall composite response. This was achieved by interrupting the tensile tests for a series of increasing strains and measuring the composite modulus at that plastic strain¹³.

2.4. Microstructural Characterisation

Following straining, metallographic sections were prepared parallel to the gauge length of the tensile specimen and were studied using optical microscopy. These specimens were then electropolished using Struers A2 electrolyte and examined in an SEM. This allowed the study of the damage processes which had occurred in the composite³. Fracture surfaces were also examined in the SEM in order to relate the microstructural damage observed on the electropolished sections to the features visible on the fracture surface. The occurrence of particle cracking in the CS composite was studied in detail, the lengths and widths of cracked and uncracked particles being compared using the SEM images of the electropolished sections of the gauge length.

2.5. Eshelby Modelling

Recent activity has shown the benefit in applying Eshelby's equivalent inclusion model to the mechanical response of metal matrix composites^{6,7}. This type of model allows a ready comparison with the neutron diffraction data because both the model and the experiment give information about the mean elastic strains and stresses in both phases of the composite. The modelling requires input of accurate mechanical property data for the individual phases of the composite. The figures used for the relevant phases are shown in table 1.

Material	Young's Modulus	Poisson's Ratio
6061 alloy ¹⁴	69.0 GPa	0.3
2618 alloy ¹⁴	74.4 GPa	0.3
Zirconia ¹⁵ †	280 GPa	0.255

Table 1. The mechanical property data used in the Eshelby model.

Figure 2. Stress / strain curves of both composites, as measured during the neutron diffraction experiments.

are superimposed in figure 2. The VPS material failed at just over 3% strain, while the CS composite had not failed when the test was finished at 4% strain. (For the latter composite the strain to failure was measured as 6% during mechanical testing on the Schenk.) It can be seen that the VPS material had significantly inferior mechanical properties when compared with the commercially produced composite both in terms of yield/tensile stress and strain to failure.

3. RESULTS

The commercially produced CS composite was chosen for comparison with the VPS material because it exhibited reinforcement cracking at relatively small strain values eg. 3% strain. This has provided us with an opportunity to compare and contrast the stress transfer characteristics for particle cracking and for interface debonding.

3.1. Mechanical Response

The stress / strain plots of the two composites as determined in the neutron diffraction tests

† The Young's Modulus of zirconia depends on the level of stabilisation and the particulate density.

Figure 3. Fracture surface of the VPS composite showing both debonding and banding.

Figure 4. Voiding at the the Al/ZrO₂ interface in the VPS composite.

Observations of the fracture surface (figure 3) and an electropolished section of the gauge length of the failed VPS composite (figure 4) clearly show the considerable debonding in this composite. Figure 5 shows the particle fracture perpendicular to the tensile axis in the CS material, which was not present in its as-processed condition and was not observed for the VPS material.

Figure 5. The onset of particle cracking at 3.7% plastic strain in the CS composite.

Measured lattice strain curves for the two composites are shown in figures 6 and 7. The maximum mean lattice strain observed for the zirconia in the VPS material was 0.0022 at the maximum applied load of 146 MPa. This compares with a mean lattice strain of 0.0041 at an applied load of 400 MPa for the zirconia in the CS material which exhibited particle cracking. Also shown in figures 6 and 7 are the predictions of the mean particle and matrix strains obtained using the Eshelby model, assuming no microstructural damage and hence perfect load transfer. Not surprisingly, in view of the damage observed for both materials, the experimentally observed lattice strains in the reinforcement are considerably lower than the values predicted by the model. This reflects both the greatly limited load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement, and the differences in the load transfer for the two materials. At high stresses the modelled load transfer is dominated in both cases by the plastically generated matrix/inclusion misfit. The mean zirconia lattice strain in the CS material before particle cracking curve up to approximately 370 MPa follows the modelled curve up to approximately 0.9% and corresponds to a stress of approximately 1 GPa in the inclusions. This must be the stress at which particle fracture becomes significant for the zirconia used here.

Figure 6. Mean lattice strains from the Eshelby model and the neutron diffraction test for the VPS composite.

Figure 7. Mean lattice strains from the Eshelby model and the neutron diffraction test for the CS composite.

Figure 8. Composite modulus variations as a function of strain.

Correlations between the composite modulus and damage level from the Eshelby model for the VPS composite allowed quantification of the debonding level as a function of the loading of the specimen⁴. Such calculations have not yet been possible for the CS material, because it is not clear how the stress will be redistributed when the particles crack. It is hoped that this type of comparison between level of cracking and stress state will be possible once the distribution of stress in a cracked particle is fully understood. However, it is clear from figure 8 that there is a significant decrease in the composite modulus arising from either form of microstructural damage, which becomes increasingly pronounced for both materials as the plastic strain is increased.

3.2. Damage Observations in the Cracked Particles

A study of the size and aspect ratio distribution of the cracked particles was conducted on the specimens which had undergone the combined mechanical/ neutron diffraction test. The overall plastic strain in the gauge length was measured with a strain gauge to be 3.2%, although there was some variation in the cross-sectional area of the gauge length along the specimen due to strain concentration. Variations in the proportion of cracked particles seen along the gauge length (figures 9 and 10) were found to correlate with the changes in local plastic strain. In one region of the gauge length, where the plastic strain was measured from the reduction in area to be 3.7% (figure 9), a significant proportion (20%) of the particles were cracked, and 3% had cracked twice. Where the plastic strain was measured as 2.2%, a significantly lower level of cracking (3%) was found, as can be seen from figure 10. The particles which had cracked at the lower of these two strain values had aspect ratios of approximately 2-3, while in the region which showed the higher local strain the aspect ratios of the cracked particles were as low as 1.2, showing that higher aspect ratio particles were the first to crack at low strains. Evidence of secondary cracking was also clear at the higher local strain level. Similarly it became clear from figure 11 that the cracked particles were generally of higher volume than the uncracked particles, as would be expected for a brittle ceramic reinforcement with a low Weibull modulus, since the probability of a defect which would cause failure is increased for larger particles.

Figure 9. Length and width distribution of the zirconia particles in the CS composite at 3.7% plastic strain.

Figure 10. Length and width distribution of the zirconia particles in the CS composite at 2.2% plastic strain.

4. DISCUSSION

Of course, either of the failure mechanisms observed in the two materials studied here would be expected to lead to poor load transfer as exhibited in the two composite systems studied here. In the case of debonding, the matrix is unable to transfer load to the reinforcement across the free surfaces between the two phases, while the stress across the cracked faces of a particle must also be zero. In the former case, the modelling work suggested that load transfer across the particle /matrix sidewall interfaces does not occur, although it seems that such load transfer is possible in the CS composite. This difference in interface behaviour may possibly be due to the longer melt/particle contact time in the CS processing route, or possibly due to the considerably greater degree of consolidation the CS composite was subjected to during secondary processing. Our neutron diffraction data has enabled us to quantify the mean stress state in the reinforcement of the two composites, and has thus demonstrated the significant degree to which the load transfer was reduced differently for the two damage mechanisms. A rough calculation of the critical crack size for fracture suggests that this is an order of magnitude greater than the size of the flaws due to either debonding or particle fracture as studied here. However, the comparison of the mechanical properties of the two composites (figure 2) shows significant differences in their overall responses. Considering the similarity in the scale of the microstructural damage in the two materials, it seems unlikely that the differences in mechanical properties are solely due to the ability of a single debonded particle in the VPS material to initiate fracture more efficiently than a single cracked particle in the CS composite. Instead it seems more likely that there is an inherent weakness in the VPS material which minimises the elastic region and encourages the fracture process. Considerable banding was seen in the VPS composite (figure 3) and may in fact be the key to the premature failure of this material, as the voids in banded regions may more easily coalesce to initiate fracture.

Figure 11. Plot of aspect ratio against particle volume for the CS composite at 3.7% plastic strain.

Figure 12. Values of the axial stress produced by the Eshelby model.

The dependence of the degree of particle cracking upon the composite plastic strain is consistent with the greater load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement associated with the larger induced misfit between the two phases. This can be explained easily from a consideration of the stress values which would be experienced by the particles under combined elastic and plastic loading. Figure 12 shows the axial stress borne by the reinforcement, as calculated by the Eshelby model, at plastic strain levels of 2.2% and 3.7% for a perfectly bonded, non-relaxed system, containing 6 vol % of ZrO₂ assuming all the particles are of a single aspect ratio. Although this is not a realistic picture, it serves to show that the stress in a particle of aspect ratio equal to 2 at a strain level of 2.2%, is the same as that in a particle of aspect ratio approximately 1.2 at a plastic strain level of 3.7%. This correlates well with the experimental observations made above, regarding the relative occurrence of particle cracking in differently strained regions of the CS specimen. This also indicates that load transfer to the lower aspect ratio/smaller particles continues once cracking has begun in the larger/high aspect ratio reinforcement.

Figure 13. Particle cracking in the region behind the fracture surface of the CS composite. There is evidence of multiple cracking perpendicular to the tensile axis as well as considerable local plastic strain, as witnessed by the opening of the cracks.

Multiple cracking is also frequently seen (figures 5 and 13) in the CS composite. This suggests that once a particle has cracked for the first time, the stress in its two halves, which will have been partially relaxed by the crack, can then increase once again until a further fracture is initiated. For the load to increase in the separate halves of a cracked particle, load transfer must be occurring across the Al/ZrO₂ end and side interfaces. It would also seem that this load transfer is relatively efficient since the proportion of multiply cracked particles is relatively high, and the length of the resulting cracked sections has been observed to be very short (ie aspect ratios are produced which can be much less than one in some cases), especially in regions to the rear of the fracture surface where the plastic strain was very high (figure 13).

composites contained zirconia particles, it is clear that the interfacial characteristics are very different. As to whether this is due to the increased melt contact time for the CS material, differences in the secondary processing, or differences in the surfaces of the two types of zirconia is not yet known.

The efficient load transfer is indicative of a strong interface for the commercially produced CS material. While both

5. CONCLUSIONS

Both composite types have shown considerable accumulation of damage upon loading. In the case of the composite produced by a VPS technique debonding was the major damage mechanism while, for the Co-sprayed composite, particle cracking dominated.

A neutron diffraction study of the lattice strains as a function of applied strain in both phases of the composites has shown how different forms of microstructural damage lead to limited load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement. For the VPS material, in which debonding dominated (detailed elsewhere⁴), the observed load transfer can be well explained by treating the debonded reinforcement as voids.

As would be expected for a brittle reinforcing phase such as zirconia, there is a tendency for cracking to be more frequent in particles with a higher volume.

The occurrence of multiple cracking illustrates that load can be transferred to the reinforcement following the initial cracking event, even though one face of the reinforcement can carry no stress component. This continuing load transfer implies that the interfacial bonding in the commercially produced 'CS' composite system is better than for the VPS material.

The occurrence of particle cracking is shown to be strongly dependent upon the aspect ratio of the reinforcement, in the CS material, and for this type of composite it is this that governs the load which the reinforcing phase will be subject to at a given level of applied stress and plastic strain. The higher the plastic strain and the greater the degree of particle cracking, the more the load has to be carried by the matrix, while simultaneously for a given uncracked particle, the greater is the load transfer even when local relaxation is taken into account.

There is a need to look further into the relationship of both the initial and subsequent cracking to factors such as aspect ratio, particle volume, local plastic strain and reinforcement clustering.

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